

USING AVERSIVE RACISM TO EXPLAIN JUROR BIAS AGAINST FILIPINO DEFENDANTS

by

Brian Saporsantos

ORCID ID: 0009-0002-2723-9006

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11479552

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton

May 2024

Approved by:

Russell Espinoza

Date:

5/6/2024

Dr. Russell Espinoza, Department of Psychology

Stacy Mallicoat

5/24/2024

Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director, University Honors Program

Abstract

Aversive racism is a contemporary form of racial prejudice that occurs when individuals express negative attitudes toward certain racial groups but use non-racial factors (socioeconomic status, legal status, etc.) to justify their decisions. Research has demonstrated a trend in American juries treating Black and Latinx defendants more punitively than White defendants. However, little is known regarding Asian defendants despite AAPI (Asian American and Pacific Islander) being the fastest-growing racial group. This study examined aversive bias with juror decisions for Filipino defendants. A mock trial was conducted to examine participants' prejudicial attitudes toward Filipino and White defendants who varied in immigration status (documented or undocumented). After reading through a trial transcript, mock juror participants were asked to render a verdict, recommend a sentence, answer various defendant culpability questions, and rate the defendant on a number of trait measures. Results showed statistical significance for legal status on sentencing and culpability. Specifically, mock jurors found undocumented immigrants more culpable compared to documented immigrants. Given the history of anti-Asian prejudice in the United States, juror bias research regarding this population is essential because these findings can have a significant impact on reducing biased juror decisions toward minority defendants.

Keywords: anti-Asian prejudice, aversive racism, Filipino defendants, immigrant status, juror-decision making, prejudicial attitudes

Using Aversive Racism to Explain Juror Bias Against Filipino Defendants

Prejudice, and theories of prejudice, have been scientifically examined throughout the history of psychological literature. Much of this literature has focused on the root of prejudice being based on some form of threat, either symbolic or realistic (Pearson, 2010; Stephan et al., 2005). When individuals from a certain group feel threatened by an outgroup, then prejudice is used as a tool to discriminate against them to reduce the threat. However, these negative attitudes towards outgroups can have drastic effects on how minorities are treated in real-life situations, such as the legal system. Although meant to be bias-free and unprejudiced, preconceived notions that jurors hold can impact how they treat and decide the fate of minority defendants, such as immigrants. When immigrant defendants are undocumented, and this fact comes out at trial, jurors are more likely to find them guilty, sentence them punitively, and find them more responsible for a crime compared with documented immigrants (Minero & Espinoza, 2015). This effect is found to have greater risks when the defendant commits a capital crime, resulting in a capital trial. Even when there is circumstantial evidence to provide a life sentence, mock capital jurors still find aggravating evidence stronger, thus deciding the death penalty more for immigrant defendants (West et al., 2020). Therefore, it is evident that prejudice, whether shown explicitly or implicitly, has great influence over a legal system that is meant to be fair and impartial.

Literature Review

Prejudice throughout the years has transformed and revealed itself in many ways, from blatant to more subtle forms of prejudice, with the latter being more common (Kite and Whitely, 2016). This could be because people in today's generation have truly developed an internal motivation to not be prejudiced or because of societal pressures to be unprejudiced, or a mixture

of both. However, whether overt or implicit, prejudice is still harmful in either form. This is especially true when it applies to the legal system, where biases and prejudices can have dire consequences. However, according to the literature that was reviewed, this is not always the case as minority defendants tend to be treated more punitively compared to non-minority defendants (Kite and Whitley, 2016). This is not surprising as the current political climate of the United States is constantly in heat when issues arise around minority groups, like LGBTQ+ rights, women's reproductive health, and antisemitism, just to name a few. Since the reign of Donald Trump, the former U.S. President, the topic of immigration became a major target for him and his supporters because of an increase of immigrants into the United States. This has led a great deal of people to view immigrants in a negative light as they view them as a threat (Pearson, 2010), which has been seen to have dire effects on juror decision-making when the defendants are immigrants (Minero & Espinoza, 2015). Therefore, the purpose of this literature review is to investigate the role that prejudice plays in court cases involving immigrant defendants.

How Threat (or Perceptions of Threat) Affect Levels of Prejudice

Before diving into the effects of prejudice in the legal system, an analysis of potential causes of prejudice will be examined. As previously mentioned, much anti-immigrant prejudice comes from this perception of a threat (Pearson, 2010). Pearson (2010) discussed the integrated threat theory (ITT), which involves a combination of realistic, symbolic, and negative stereotype threats. Realistic threats jeopardize the welfare of a group, either politically or economically, due to competition over resources (Pearson, 2010). On the other hand, Pearson (2010) describes symbolic threats as a group's values that jeopardize another group's morals and traditional standards. The main differences between these two are that realistic threats involve tangible competition while symbolic threats involve opposing worldviews. Integrated threat theory adds

negative stereotypes as a type of threat because they can lead to one's failures if taken to be true (Pearson, 2010). These are the main theories of threat that are believed to be a driving force for prejudice.

Pearson (2010) conducted a study that looked at how ITT and the instrumental model of group conflict (IMGC) affect levels of prejudice when certain words are used to describe Mexican immigrants, "illegal aliens" or "undocumented workers". IMGC looks at perceived competition and outlines social dominance orientation (SDO) as a guiding theory (Pearson, 2010). Kite and Whitley (2016) describe SDO as a belief system about one's own group being superior and remaining superior no matter the means. Therefore, IMGC looks more at perceived competition while ITT reports more on perceived threat, which both can be causes of prejudice. In Pearson (2010)'s study, 269 undergraduate psychology students were asked to report their opinions towards "Mexican immigrants", which the term would be replaced with "illegal aliens" or "undocumented workers" depending on the condition. Afterward, participants completed a questionnaire that examined measures related to ITT and IMGC. Results of the study show that "illegal aliens" produced more prejudice, and it is best explained by ITT. What these findings mean is that the term "illegal aliens" increases prejudice because of perceptions of a greater threat (Pearson, 2010). Therefore, how Mexican immigrants are described in the media can have drastic effects on how consumers view this group, especially when the terms used to describe them fulfill consumers' beliefs they hold about immigrants. This perceived threat provides a possible explanation for why immigrant defendants are treated differently compared to those who are non-immigrants.

Similarly, Stephan et al. (2005) conducted three studies that tested the integrated threat theory on people's views towards immigrants and also added intergroup anxiety as a factor for

anti-immigrant attitudes. Each study was performed similarly in that participants were given information about an immigrant group and were tested on different measures via questionnaires or interviews. The first study measured the effects of realistic and symbolic threats, together and separately. The second study used negative stereotypes to analyze a potential cause of prejudice. The third study looked at intergroup anxiety and how feelings of anxiousness towards outgroups can possibly lead to negative attitudes. Evidently, the first two studies relate to ITT because Pearson (2010) similarly examined realistic threats, symbolic threats, and negative stereotypes as well and obtained similar results. Just like Pearson (2010)'s findings, the first study found that both realistic and symbolic threats provided the most negative attitudes, and the second study found that negative attitudes caused participants to view immigrants more negatively (Stephan et al., 2005).

Intergroup anxiety, which is feelings of anxiousness towards outgroups (Stephan et al., 2005), adds to the ITT because those who experience anxiety around members of groups they do not have much experience with may be more prejudiced. Stephan et al. (2005)'s third study supports intergroup anxiety as a factor for prejudice as they found that participants evaluated foreign exchange students more negatively when intergroup anxiety was high. This anxiety fits within the context of threat because both led to increases in prejudice towards immigrants and foreigners. Therefore, when people have fewer interactions with an outgroup, this can cause feelings of anxiety, which could then turn into feelings of threat because these individuals do not have enough experience interacting with immigrants. Overall, both these studies provide a basis for the development of prejudice towards immigrants, with the perception of a threat playing a major role (Pearson, 2010; Stephan et al., 2005).

Immigrant Status and Prejudiced Jurors

Now that a possible cause of anti-immigrant prejudice has been defined, it is time to examine this prejudice within the context of the legal system, specifically within jurors. Minero and Espinoza (2015) observed this phenomenon in their study where they varied the immigration status, country of origin, and ethnicity of the defendant to examine if a certain combination is treated differently compared to the other conditions. The purpose of their study was to determine if immigrant status affected juror decisions, and if the country of origin and ethnicity acted as the driving factors for this juror bias.

Participants in Minero and Espinoza (2015)'s study acted as mock jurors deciding in a fictitious court trial. The trial packet contained a description of the case and charges against the defendant, which was the same for all participants. The only differing variables were the defendant's immigrant status (legal or illegal), country of origin (Canada or Mexico), and ethnicity (White or Latino) (Minero & Espinoza, 2015). Participants are asked to render a verdict, suggest a sentence, define the culpability of the defendant, and rate personality traits of the defendant. The purpose of changing the three variables and keeping the remaining information about the trial the same is for the examination of prejudice to occur. Since the only changes being made are related to the racial and immigrant status of the defendant, then it is plausible to deduce that negative treatment towards the minority would find a cause in prejudiced juror decision-making skills. This prediction turned out to be true as European American jurors acted the most prejudiced toward Latino defendants from Mexico who were undocumented (Minero & Espinoza, 2015). A finding like this negates a supposedly "trial by an impartial jury" as stated in the Sixth Amendment of the Bill of Rights, which is significant because immigrant defendants are being treated more punitively due to juror's biases, and this puts them at a

disadvantage within the legal system. These findings should be treated gravely because this juror bias found in common court trials can also play a role in capital punishment cases.

Immigrant Status of Defendant vs. Capital Punishment

Capital punishment involves the sentencing of offenders of the most serious crimes; therefore, juror bias holds higher stakes in these cases because an immigrant defendant's life is at the hands of the jury (West et al., 2020). Jurors in a capital trial go through a bifurcated process, or two stages: (1) guilt verdict and (2) weighing aggravators and mitigators to determine a life sentence or death punishment (West et al., 2020). Aggravators are information that supports the death penalty cause, while mitigators support a life sentence verdict (Costanzo & Krauss, 2021). Having to decide between what constitutes an aggravator and a mitigator can take up a lot of cognitive processing on jurors because it can lead them to rely on their prejudices to influence their decisions.

West et al. (2020) studied this juror bias toward immigrants in capital cases. The purpose of their study was to examine how the immigrant status and ethnicity of a defendant affect how mock jurors view the evidence presented to them as either aggravators or mitigators. Participants in this study read through a trial summary, in which all information except the defendant's immigrant status, ethnicity, and evidence strength varied, and then were asked to weigh the evidence and choose a sentence. Afterward, they were measured on their cognitive processing. The results of West et al. (2020)'s study support prior research defined in this literature review as mock jurors found aggravators to overrule the mitigators when the defendant was undocumented, even if the case they received listed more mitigators. This means that, in most cases, all odds are against immigrant defendants in capital trials due to biased juror decisions even when there is more information to support a life sentence. The results of this study highlight a significant issue

within the U.S. legal system. The courts of law are supposed to bring true justice to those involved in a case, but, as described in the current literature, jurors influenced by their biases continue to make decisions that negatively impact minority defendants.

Implications and Further Research

These findings truly show the horrific effects unchecked prejudice has on immigrant defendants as they will likely be treated more punitively. Of course, non-immigrant and non-minority defendants can be treated poorly as well. However, current research and literature point to higher cases of immigrants being treated worse; therefore, the legal system must become proactive in reducing levels of prejudice if it wants to provide justice effectively. Workers of the legal system, such as judges, lawyers, legislators, and other legal consultants, must actively work against expressing biases. This could potentially aid in the reduction of juror bias as judges could inform the jury of the effects that one's prejudice can have and how to control them. Lastly, further research calls for more analysis of other ethnic immigrant defendants, such as Asians, as the immigrant population continues to increase.

Current Study

The purpose of this study is to examine how ethnicity (White or Filipino) and immigrant status (documented and undocumented) interact to affect decisions made by jurors.

Hypotheses

Based on the theory of aversive racism, we expect that mock jurors will demonstrate prejudice against undocumented Filipino defendants. Specifically, the four hypotheses of the study are: (1) Mock jurors will find this defendant guilty significantly more often compared to the other conditions; (2) Mock jurors will recommend lengthier sentences compared with the other conditions; (3) Mock jurors will find this defendant more culpable compared with the

other conditions; and (4) Mock jurors will rate this defendant more negatively on a number of trait ascription measures compared with the other conditions.

Method

Participants

Seventy-five undergraduate psychology students from a large Southern California university participated as mock jurors in this study. Participants were recruited from a psychology department research pool using Sona Systems, an online experiment management system. All participants were 18 years of age or older with a mean age of 20.70. No other exclusionary criteria were used for this study. Majority of the participants were female (65.8%, $n = 48$) with the other participants identifying as male (31.5%, $n = 23$) and trans (2.7%, $n = 2$). Racial makeup of the mock juror consisted of Latinx American (54.8%, $n = 40$), Asian American (13.7%, $n = 10$), White (9.6%, $n = 7$), African American (8.2%, $n = 6$), and other unlisted backgrounds (13.7%, $n = 10$).

Materials and Procedure

Participants completed the study in-person in a research lab with up to three other participants at a time, per timeslot. The only requirement to partake in the study was for participants to be at least 18 years of age or older. This was done in order to align with the minimum age requirement to be on a jury in the state of California. Participants were instructed to treat this study as if they were jurors in an actual criminal trial.

Before beginning the study, mock jurors were given informed consent forms to educate them on their rights as participants as well as inform them on the contents of the study. Such rights included the confidentiality of their answers and being able to stop participating in the study at any time if they felt uncomfortable. Once they consented to being a part of the study,

participants were then randomly assigned one of four conditions in a 2 (Defendant race: Filipino or White/Canadian) x 2 (Documentation status: documented or undocumented) between-subjects design.

For the mock trial study, participants read a fictional vignette that was designed to resemble a trial transcript. A picture of the male defendant was depicted at the top of the first page. His name, age, sex, and race, as well as the charges pressed against him, were defined under the photo. The photo of the defendant was varied, with it either depicting a White or a Filipino individual. In addition, the name was also varied to reflect the racial makeup of the defendant, with Michael LeFlore being assigned to the White defendant and Daniel Rivera being assigned to the Filipino defendant. The following pages detailed the case summary of the crime that was allegedly committed (murder in the first degree). In addition, the defendant's background was described, which included information revealing his immigrant status (documented or undocumented), as well as his plea of "Not guilty," which was the same across all conditions. Lastly, statements from both prosecution and defense were detailed.

With both racial makeup and immigrant status defined, participants were assigned to one of the following defendant conditions: undocumented Filipino, documented Filipino, undocumented White, and documented White. The trial transcript detailed that the White defendant immigrated from Canada and the Filipino defendant immigrated from the Philippines. The description of the crime and overall trial case was created with established measures in psychology and law (Minero & Espinoza, 2015; Phan et al., 2022). In terms of the crime itself, the evidence and eyewitness testimonies suggested support for both guilty and innocent verdicts. The unclarity of the presented evidence was to induce the participants into implicitly incorporating their biases in their decisions as jurors. Following the case

summaries from the defense and prosecution were the closing arguments from both sides.

Before deciding on a verdict, the mock jurors read “General Juror Instructions,” which detailed specific requirements that must be met before concluding with a guilty verdict. The requirements resembled legal requirements to convict someone of murder of the first degree, which are that (1) the defendant willfully killing the victim, (2) the defendant was acting on his own accord, and (3) no other explanation or suspect is reasonable possible. Participants then rendered a verdict (Guilty or Not Guilty). If a guilty verdict was found, then participants were asked to recommend a sentence. The sentencing options were one of the following: (a) Ten year prison sentence with the possibility of parole after 20 years, (b) Life in prison with the possibility of parole after 30 years and time for good behavior, or (c) Life in prison without the possibility of parole.

Once a verdict and sentence, if applicable, were decided on, then the participants were asked to rate the defendant’s culpability for the crime. The culpability items were created based on similar research testing juror bias (Phan et al., 2022). The following culpability measures were used: How guilty do you think the defendant actually is? How long of a sentence do you think the defendant should actually receive? In your own opinion, how responsible is the defendant for committing this crime? How confident are you that you have made a correct guilt decision? How likely is it that the defendant will commit this crime again in the future? How much do you believe the defendant’s version of the crime? How likely is it that you would find yourself in a similar situation as the defendant? How much of the blame for the incident should the defendant receive? How likely is it that the defendant committed this same crime in the past? How much did the situation influence the defendant’s behavior? If you found the defendant guilty, to what degree do you think the defendant intentionally meant

to kill the victim? To what degree do you think the defendant lied to the police? How much did the viciousness of the attacks impact your decision? How much did the defendant being an immigrant impact your decision? All items were measured on a seven-point Likert-type scale.

After completing the culpability measures, the mock jurors were asked to rate the defendant on a variety of trait measures. The trait measures were also developed using prior research examining juror bias (Phan et al., 2022). The following trait items were used: trustworthiness, likeability, competence, ethicalness, selfishness, attractiveness, intelligence, cold/warm, sensitivity, laziness/industriousness, and aggression. All items were measured on a seven-point Likert-type scale.

To ensure that participants comprehended the information of the trial, a “Juror Memory Form” manipulation check was included. Without referring to the case, participants were tested on their memory of basic facts about the case. Questions included: (1) Where did the defendant live?, (2) Please rate the social/economic status of the defendant (1 = low, 9 = high), (3) What was the defendant’s racial or ethnic background?, (4) What was the weapon used to kill the victim?, (5) Where did the crime take place? Finally, participants filled out a “Juror Background Form” to provide basic demographic information about themselves. Such information included racial background, political affiliation, religion, and yearly income.

Results

This mock juror study examined four main dependent variables: verdict, recommended sentence, culpability ratings, and trait ratings. To determine the effects of defendant legal status and race on the categorical variables of verdict and sentence, two series of logit chi-square analyses were conducted. To determine the effects of defendant legal status and race on the continuous variables of culpability and trait ratings, two two-way MANOVA analyses were

conducted. Two participants were excluded from the analyses due to incomplete responses on the survey.

Verdict

Contrary to the first hypothesis, the logit chi-square analysis found no significant differences based on the combined effects of defendant race and documentation status on juror verdicts, $\chi^2(3) = 1.61, p = .66$. Additionally, no main effects were found ($p > .05$).

Recommended Sentence

The mock jurors who found the defendant guilty ($n = 39$) were required to recommend a sentence: Ten-year prison sentence with the possibility of parole after 20 years, life in prison with the possibility of parole after 30 years and time for good behavior, or life in prison without the possibility of parole. A significant main effect for documentation status on prison sentencing was found, $\chi^2(2) = 6.20, p = .05$. Although significance was found, mock jurors who found the defendant guilty were more likely to sentence the undocumented defendants more leniently compared with the documented defendants. Additionally, no significant two-way interactions were found ($p > .05$).

Culpability Ratings

Results for the MANOVA analysis for culpability demonstrated a significant main effect for documentation status on culpability, $F(14, 43) = .57, p = .02$. Follow-up univariate analyses demonstrated significant effects for the Likert-type culpability measures of same crime in past, $F(1, 70) = 5.33, p = .02$, and defendant being an immigrant, $F(1, 69) = 3.85, p = .05$. Participants found the undocumented defendants to be more likely to have committed the same crime in the past and them being an immigrant influenced the mock jurors' ratings. No significant two-way interactions were found ($p > .05$).

Trait Ratings

Contrary to the fourth hypothesis, the two-way MANOVA analysis found no significant interactions for documentation status and defendant race, $F(11, 52) = 1.71, p = .10$. However, follow-up univariate analyses for defendant race demonstrated significant effects for the Likert-type trait measures of warmth, $F(1, 70) = 23.84, p = .01$, and aggression, $F(1, 70) = 18.21, p = .03$. Additionally, follow-up ANOVA analysis for the combined effects of defendant race and documentation status demonstrated significant effects for ratings of competence, $F(1, 68) = 16.00, p < .001$. Participants rated the Filipino defendant as more warm and less aggressive compared to the White defendant. In addition, participants rated the undocumented Filipino defendant as most competent compared to the other defendants: documented Filipino, undocumented White, and documented White. Lastly, no significant main effects were found ($p > .05$).

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to examine the effects of defendant race and defendant documentation status on juror decisions from an aversive racism perspective for Filipino and Canadian immigrant defendants. We hypothesized that the mock jurors would make biased decisions against the undocumented Filipino defendant by (1) finding this defendant guilty more often compared with the other defendants; (2) recommending lengthier sentences compared with the other defendants; (3) finding this defendant more culpable compared with the other defendants; and (4) rating this defendant more negatively on a variety of trait characteristic measures compared with the other defendants. Although results of the study did not find support for hypothesis one, two, and four, our findings did support hypothesis three. Additionally, even with insignificant statistical results for hypothesis one and four, we were still able to observe

patterns in the data that suggest support for the respective hypotheses. Explanations for these patterns will be detailed further.

As the results of the study show, the mock jurors in this study assigned more culpability to the undocumented defendants (White and Filipino) compared to the documented defendants, which supports the third hypothesis. More specifically, the mock jurors found the undocumented defendants to be more likely to have committed the same crime in the past and that them being an immigrant influenced their ratings of the defendant. Interestingly enough, examining the data of the culpability MANOVA even further reveal that the undocumented Filipino was rated slightly harsher compared with the documented Filipino for the culpability measures “same crime in the past” and “defendant being an immigrant.” Even though the results for within the racial category of Filipino found no significance, there is still a pattern of the undocumented Filipino being treated differently compared with the documented Filipino. With the controversy surrounding undocumented immigrants in the United States, it seems plausible that mock jurors would use the defendant’s immigrant status to explain their higher culpability ratings for the racial minority defendant. Because aversive racism proposes that jurors will exhibit prejudice when race is paired with a perceived negative variable, then this pattern suggests that the theory of aversive racism is at play because the only difference between the two defendants is their documentation status.

As for hypothesis one, we were unable to find statistical significance for the combination of documentation status and race on verdict. However, through reviewing the numerical data of the verdict decisions, we noticed that there were more guilty verdicts for the undocumented defendant. This pattern is substantial because maybe with more participants in our sample would we have possibly gotten significant findings. Typically, the data sample of a study should

represent the target population; however, with a low number of participants, this most likely explains why we were unable to obtain statistical significance. Low power in this study will be explained further in the limitations section.

Similar to hypothesis one, hypothesis four concluded with no significant interactions or main effects but, after analyzing the data, patterns of possibly stereotyping towards the undocumented and Filipino defendant are visible. When conducting individual ANOVA tests on the trait measures, we were able to find significance for defendant race on the following traits: cold/warm and aggression. More specifically, the mock jurors of the study rated the Filipino defendant as warmer and less aggressive compared to the White defendant. This overall rating of Filipinos as being warm and less aggressive hints towards a common career choice that many Filipinos take part in, which is healthcare. Many Filipinos are nurses, which are jobs that require healthcare workers to care for their patients. With the high number of Filipino healthcare workers, then this caring attribute could possibly be what these mock jurors associate Filipinos to be. If true, then this finding is still important because jurors would be using stereotypes about Filipinos to rate the defendant when they should be rating the defendant as an individual themselves.

Continuing with the individual ANOVA test for trait measures, we also found statistical significance for the combination of defendant race and documentation status on the following trait: competence. Reviewing the data, the mock jurors rated the undocumented Filipino as most competent, the documented White as second, the documented Filipino as third, and the undocumented White as least competent. Out of the four defendant conditions, the undocumented Filipino defendant was viewed as the most competent. This is an interesting finding because those that are undocumented in the United States tend to be viewed as

uneducated and incapable to be functioning members of society. Therefore, participants rating the undocumented Filipino defendant as most competent negates this common perspective. A possible explanation for this goes back again to Filipinos being in healthcare.

There is a long history of the United States importing nurses from the Philippines, and it even got to the point where nursing schools were built by the U.S. to teach them Western medicine (Wright, 2021). To this day, the U.S. is still reliant on Overseas Filipino Workers (OFW), which includes other occupations like construction, cleaners, and factory workers. Therefore, not only are they Filipinos but they are also undocumented workers. Because of this strong reliance of OFWs, it seems possible that the mock jurors rated the undocumented Filipino defendant as most competent for this reason. In addition, there is also the common *model minority myth*, which is the stereotype that Asians are the most successful of all minorities in society, hence why they are the “model minority.” Because of this phenomenon, some of the mock jurors could also have possibly attributed the Filipino defendant to being a “good minority,” even though they were alleged to have committed a murder. Again, an important observation because, if true, then participants were viewing the undocumented Filipino more leniently because of the common stereotypes rather than rating them as an individual.

One unexpected finding arose when we analyzed data for hypothesis two. We hypothesized that the undocumented, Filipino immigrant would be sentenced harsher. However, a significant main effect for documentation status on sentencing revealed that the mock jurors sentenced the undocumented defendant more leniently compared to the documented defendant. Although we found statistical significance in the data for sentencing, we found results that countered our expectations. Through analyzing the demographic makeup of the mock jurors, a possible explanation for this unexpected finding would be because the data sample we worked

with was overwhelmingly ethnic minorities. Over half of our participants identified as Latinx, and with the combination of living in Southern California, we postulate that the topic of immigration is a factor that the participants are familiar with. Whether through a direct experience or by knowing someone who is an immigrant, we propose that the mock jurors sentenced the undocumented defendant more leniently because it is a relevant topic in their lives. In addition, all the participants were psychology students who were selected from a Southern California university. Therefore, we also postulate that both, Southern California and psychology, are more progressive- and liberal-leaning areas, which is why we think the participants were more lenient towards the undocumented defendant.

Though our results did not provide statistical significance for three of our hypotheses, patterns in the data still suggested biased decisions and ratings based on stereotypes and personal experience. From the undocumented defendant being rated more culpable to the Filipino defendant being rated as warmer, it seems that the participants relied on common perceptions of both Filipinos and undocumented individuals while completing the study. Overall, the data of our study began to approach significance and support for our hypotheses, which indicates that improvements shall be made to secure more findings for this study.

Limitations and Future Directions

The biggest issue regarding our study was that we needed more power when it came to our participant make up. Power refers to the ability to reject the null hypothesis when it is false, which basically means the probability that our hypothesis is correct. A major component of having sufficient power would be to have a data sample that accurately represents the target population being studied. Due to only have seventy-five participants in our study, we lacked enough power to verify that our findings are statistically significant. Therefore, future directions

for this study would be to obtain a greater number of participants so that we have a better representation of the “real world,” which happens to be the U.S. jury pool population. This is important because with a data sample with a Latinx majority, it is harder to obtain the results we want. This is especially true when prior research on aversive racism in the legal system have found significance when their data samples were large and also included more White participants (Minero & Espinoza, 2015). Because aversive racism has been viewed as occurring more with White participants, this would mean possibly conducting this study to other areas and demographics to have more representation.

Other areas of interest would be cities with greater White populations as well as Asians and African Americans. It would also be interesting to outreach to other majors as well, like business and engineering, since only psychology majors were examined. Lastly, I would also suggest for future studies to include a greater variety in age groups as participants in this study were mostly young adults at the time when taking the study. Overall, studies similar to this one would need to include a much larger and more diverse data sample so that they are working with a representative sample of the American jury pool system. In addition, aside from power, a diverse, representative sample would also allow us to generalize our findings to the greater American population.

Finally, despite the lack of statistical support, the results of this study have broader implications for the legal system in the United States. The American jury should be impartial and unbiased; however, research on juror bias in the legal system continues to highlight inconsistencies with that statement. In this study, we were able to demonstrate that undocumented immigrants themselves face scrutiny when it comes to standing trial in the court system. When race is added into the mixture, it seems like these biases trickle down even further

for ethnic minority defendants who are immigrants. We were also able to demonstrate that both documentation status and racial makeup can have an effect on how jurors rate and view specific defendants on different measures from culpability to characteristics. Overall, it is crucial for legal workers, such as judges, lawyers, legislators, and other legal consultants, to understand the importance of these findings to better improve the legal system. Understanding how biases from our society play significant roles in the jury will not only improve the ethical foundation of the law, it will ensure that minorities are heard and represented in these ongoing issues that occur in all aspects of life.

References

- Costanzo, M., & Krauss, D. A. (2021). *Forensic and legal psychology: Psychological science applied to law*. Worth Publishers.
- Kite, M. E., & Whitley, B. E. (2016). *Psychology of prejudice and discrimination* (3rd ed.). Routledge: U.S.
- Minero, L. P., & Espinoza, R. K. E. (2015). The influence of defendant immigration status, country of origin, and ethnicity on juror decisions. *Hispanic Journal of Behavioral Sciences*, 38(1), 55–74. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739986315620374>
- Pearson, M. R. (2010). How “undocumented workers” and “illegal aliens” affect prejudice toward Mexican immigrants. *Social Influence*, 5(2), 118–132. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15534511003593679>
- Phan, D. K., Espinoza, R. K. E., & Sy, S. R. (2022). An aversive racism explanation for the influence of race, SES, and race-stereotypical crimes on jury decision biases against East Asian American defendants. *Journal of Ethnicity in Criminal Justice*, 20(1), 73–95. <https://doi-org.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/10.1080/15377938.2022.2054890>
- Stephan, W. G., Renfro, C.L., Esses, V. M., Stephan, C.W., & Martin, T. (2005). The effects of feeling threatened on attitudes toward immigrants. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 29(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2005.04.011>
- West, M. P., Wood, E. F., Miller, M. K., & Bornstein, B. H. (2020). How mock jurors’ cognitive processing and defendants’ immigrant status and ethnicity relate to decisions in Capital Trials. *Journal of Experimental Criminology*, 17(3), 423–432. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11292-020-09411-4>

Wright, K. (2021). *Filipino and Filipino American nurses in the United States*. University of Washington School of Nursing. <https://nursing.uw.edu/article/filipinos-and-filipinos-americans-nurses-in-the-united-states/#:~:text=The%20U.S.%20has%20a%20long,teach%20western%20medicine%20in%20English.>